

Metal Complexes of 2-(2-Thiazolylazo)-1,3-dicarbonyls

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Manuscript received 17 May 1994. accepted 25 November 1994

A new series of heterocyclic azo compounds have been synthesised by coupling diazotised 2-aminothiazol with 1,3-dicarbonyl compounds-acetylacetone, benzoylacetone, trifluoroacetylacetone, thenoyltrifluoroactone, methyl acetoacetate and acetoacetamide. The compounds exist in the azo-enol tautomeric form. Neutral complexes of these ligands with Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} have been synthesised and characterised. Monobasic tridentate coordination of the ligands is established.

Metal complexes of azo compounds containing heteroaryl ring systems find various applications¹. Majority of these compounds are derived from the coupling of diazotised heterocyclic amines with aromatic hydroxy and amino compounds. Several types of active methylene compounds, such as 1,3-dicarbonyls are known² to couple with carbocyclic aryl diazonium ion to form compounds having interesting structural properties and uses³. Structurally, the arylazo derivatives of 1,3-dicarbonyl compounds exist in the intramolecularly hydrogen-bonded 1,2,3-tricarbonyl-2-arylhydrazones rather than the azo tautomeric form^{4,5}. Metal complexes of these hydrazones have also been investigated^{5,6}. However, reports are scanty on heteroarylazo derivatives of 1,3-dicarbonyls and their metal complexes. Details on the synthesis and characterisation of 2-(2-thiazolylazo)-1,3-dicarbonyls and their Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes are presented, the 1,3-dicarbonyls used being acetylacetone, trifluoroacetylacetone, benzoylacetone, thenoyltrifluoroacetone, methyl acetoacetate and acetoacetamide.

Results and Discussion

Elemental analytical data of the thiazolylazo derivatives of the 1,3-dicarbonyl compounds (Table 1) indicate that diazo-coupling occurred in the ratio 1 : 1 in all the cases. All the compounds are coloured yellow, crystalline in nature and soluble in common organic solvents. It has been shown that thiazolylazo derivatives of phenols and naphthalenols exist predominantly in the azohydroxy form⁷ whereas

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE DICARBONYLS AND METAL COMPLEXES

Compd. (M.p., °C)	Analysis : Found/(Calcd.)			
	C	H	N	M
Htaa (118)	45.50 (45.50)	4.30 4.40	19.95 18.10	
Httfa (116)	57.15 (57.00)	4.10 3.80	14.40 13.10	
Htba (132)	57.10 (56.50)	4.00 3.70	14.40 12.10	
Htta (130)	39.65 (38.00)	18.10 2.20	12.60 14.60	
Htma (98)	38.80 (42.00)	2.98 3.80	26.50 18.50	
Htan (145)	52.60 (54.10)	4.20 4.20	19.90 19.40	
[Co(taa) ₂] (280)	40.20 (40.09)	3.10 3.34	17.10 17.54	11.80 12.30
[Co(tfa) ₂] (230)	33.15 (32.71)	1.65 1.70	13.45 14.31	9.75 10.04
[Co(tba) ₂] (190)	50.95 (51.75)	3.10 3.31	12.50 13.93	9.20 9.76
[Co(tta) ₂] (215)	36.15 (36.51)	1.55 1.38	10.75 11.61	7.25 8.15
[Co(tma) ₂] (>300)	37.10 (37.59)	3.00 3.13	15.95 17.44	10.30 11.52
[Co(tan) ₂] (>300)	49.50 (49.30)	3.10 3.47	17.15 17.70	8.25 9.30
[Ni(taa) ₂] (240)	40.00 (40.10)	3.17 3.34	16.80 17.55	11.55 12.6
[Ni(tfa) ₂] (200)	32.15 (32.72)	2.50 1.70	13.40 14.32	9.25 10.01
[Ni(tba) ₂] (180)	51.20 (51.76)	3.15 3.31	12.80 13.93	9.05 9.73
[Ni(tta) ₂] (210)	36.05 (36.52)	1.58 1.38	10.55 11.62	7.50 8.12
[Ni(tma) ₂] (>300)	37.20 (37.60)	3.05 3.13	15.20 16.45	10.95 11.49
[Ni(tan) ₂] (265)	50.02 (49.31)	3.62 3.47	16.4 17.70	8.85 9.27

Table 1 (Contd.)

[Cu(taa)(OAc)]	36.90	3.35	15.20	18.50
(>300)	(36.09)	3.30	12.63	19.09)
[Cu(tfa)(OAc)]	39.85	1.95	10.55	16.50
(>300)	(39.05)	2.06	10.87	16.43)
[Cu(tba)(OAc)]	45.20	3.10	10.10	16.00
(200)	(45.63)	3.29	10.65	16.09)
[Cu(tta)(OAc)]	33.10	1.50	8.70	13.45
(240)	(34.32)	1.76	9.34	13.97)
[Cu(tma)(OAc)]	33.85	3.01	12.50	18.50
(>300)	(34.43)	3.16	12.09	18.32)
[Cu(tan)(OAc)]	43.20	3.32	13.30	15.05
(>300)	(43.95)	3.41	13.68	15.57)
[Zn(taa) ₂]	39.02	3.20	16.10	12.70
(250)	(39.55)	3.29	17.30	13.47)
[Zn(tfa) ₂]	31.90	1.65	13.12	10.25
(>300)	(32.36)	1.69	14.15	11.02)
[Zn(tba) ₂]	50.50	3.15	12.25	9.55
(250)	(51.18)	3.28	13.76	10.73)
[Zn(tta) ₂]	35.80	1.50	10.25	8.15
(195)	(36.20)	1.37	11.52	8.96)
[Zn(tma) ₂]	36.50	3.12	15.24	11.95
(300)	(37.11)	3.09	16.23	12.64)
[Zn(tan) ₂]	48.25	3.55	16.40	9.45
(>300)	(48.80)	3.44	17.52	10.23)

phenylazo derivatives of the 1,3-dicarbonyls exist entirely in hydrazone-keto form^{4,5}. Comparison of the reported spectral data of these compounds with that of the thiazolylazo derivatives of the 1,3-dicarbonyls shows that the latter compounds exist in the azo-enol form (1) rather than in any other alternate tautomeric forms.

Compd.	R ₁	R ₂	M = Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II} and Zn ^{II}
Htaa	CH ₃	CH ₃	
Htfa	CH ₃	CF ₃	
Htba	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	
Htta	C ₄ H ₃ S	CF ₃	
Htma	CH ₃	OCH ₃	
Htan	CH ₃	NHC ₆ H ₅	

Important ir spectral bands below 2 000 cm⁻¹ of the compounds are given in Table 2. Among these the highest frequency band can be confidently assigned to

stretching of free conjugated R₂CO. From the observed values it is possible to distinguish whether R₁CO or R₂CO remains free in the case of unsymmetrical 1,3-dicarbonyls. Thus the band at 1 725 cm⁻¹ of Htfa is due to free CF₃CO because this value is much higher than that expected^{4,8} for a free conjugated CH₃CO. The same is true in the case of Htta, the band at 1 720 cm⁻¹ being assigned to ν_{C=O} of free CF₃CO. In the case of Htba, the band at 1 650 cm⁻¹ is due to the stretching of the benzoyl carbonyl. In the spectra of Htma and Htan no band assignable to free CH₃CO is present. Thus it appears that the less electron-rich carbonyl remains free in unsymmetrical dicarbonyls.

The spectra of all the compounds display a strong and slightly broadened band at ~1 600 cm⁻¹ and a medium intensity band at ~1 620 cm⁻¹ assignable^{8,9} respectively, to ν_{C=C} and cyclic ν_{C=N}. A band at ~1 450 cm⁻¹ consistently present in the spectra of all the compounds is characteristic of typical azo structures^{8,9}. Several prominent bands appeared at ~1 520 and 1 400 cm⁻¹ assigned to the thiazole ring vibrations. The spectra of compounds containing CF₃ group show characteristic absorptions at ~1 290 and 1 010 cm⁻¹. The hydrogen-bonded nature of the hydroxy proton is evident from the presence of a very broad band at 2 500–3 500 cm⁻¹.

The ¹H nmr spectra of all the compounds show a low field one-proton signal around 14 ppm due to the acidic proton^{4,5,10}. The extremely large chemical shift of this proton indicates strong internal hydrogen bonding. The position and integrated intensities of all other signals (Table 3) are in accord with structure 1 of the compounds. The spectrum of Htaa shows two methyl proton signals of equal intensity indicating that the two are in different electronic environment. That in Htba the acetyl rather than the benzoyl group is enolised is shown by the very close value of its OH proton signal to that of Htaa. The ¹³C nmr spectrum of Htaa clearly indicates its existence in the azo-enol form. That the two acetyl groups are in different electronic environment is evident from the large separation of the methyl carbon signals (26.388 and 31.690 ppm) and the carbonyl carbon signals (195.020 and 197.989 ppm). The number and position of all other

TABLE 2-CHARACTERISTIC IR BANDS (CM⁻¹) OF THE DICARBONYLS AND THEIR METAL COMPLEXES

Compd.	C=O	C=N	C=C	N=N	C-N	C-O	M-N	M-O
Htaa	1 685	1 622	1 605, 1 598	1 445	1 280	1 208	-	-
Httfa	1 705	1 612	1 600, 1 590	1 432	1 268	1 185	-	-
Htba	1 652	1 620	1 605, 1 595	1 440	1 282	1 210	-	-
Htta	1 710	1 618	1 598, 1 592	1 435	1 275	1 190	-	-
Htma	1 726	1 615	1 608, 1 590	1 452	1 278	1 212	-	-
Htan	1 672	1 610	1605, 1 590	1 462	1 270	1 205	-	-
[Co(taa) ₂]	1 678	1 618	1 608, 1 598	1 428	1 265	1 095	562, 542	432
[Co(ttfa) ₂]	1 712	1 612	1 605, 1 592	1 420	1 255	1 088	548, 536	418
[Co(tba) ₂]	1 648	1 610	1 600, 1 590	1 412	1 270	1 105	550, 532	425
[Co(tta) ₂]	1 710	1 615	1 607, 1 598	1 415	1 262	1 090	545, 540	420
[Co(tma) ₂]	1 715	1 612	1 598, 1 592	1 435	1 258	1 094	558, 552	430
[Co(tan) ₂]	1 668	1 608	1 595, 1 590	1 442	1 258	1 102	540, 528	422
[Ni(taa) ₂]	1 685	1 612	1 605, 1 598	1 422	1 268	1 108	555, 540	426
[Ni(ttfa) ₂]	1 710	1 615	1 600, 1 595	1 418	1 272	1 095	548, 542	428
[Ni(tba) ₂]	1 652	1 605	1 598, 1 592	1 420	1 270	1 100	552, 545	430
[Ni(tta) ₂]	1 705	1 615	1 602, 1 590	1 425	1 277	1 092	563, 545	422
[Ni(tma) ₂]	1 718	1 608	1 605, 1 590	1 428	1 265	1 114	550, 536	419
[Ni(tan) ₂]	1 670	1 612	1 602, 1 592	1 432	1 268	1 105	557, 542	420
[Cu(taa)(OAc)]	1 682, 1 622, 1 305	1 605	1 598, 1 590	1 428	1 272	1 105	552, 536	425, 295
[Cu(ttfa)(OAc)]	1 708, 1 615, 1 295	1 608	1 595, 1 590	1 415	1 268	1 090	545, 530	418, 305
[Cu(tba)(OAc)]	1 655, 1 618, 1 305	1 610	1 602, 1 595	1 422	1 275	1 102	548, 538	420, 308
[Cu(tta)(OAc)]	1 705, 1 617, 1 305	1 605	1 600, 1 595	1 420	1 270	1 095	555, 535	428, 305
[Cu(tma)(OAc)]	1 720, 1 625, 1 302	1 612	1 598, 1 590	1 435	1 278	1 110	550, 540	422, 295
[Cu(tan)(OAc)]	1 675, 1 620, 1 300	1 610	1 598, 1 592	1 440	1 265	1 115	548, 542	415, 290
[Zn(taa) ₂]	1 680	1 620	1 605, 1 598	1 432	1 268	1 097	548, 540	422
[Zn(ttfa) ₂]	1 715	1 605	1 598, 1 590	1 428	1 262	1 095	538, 535	425
[Zn(tba) ₂]	1 655	1 612	1 600, 1 595	1 420	1 268	1 102	545, 542	412
[Zn(tta) ₂]	1 712	1 608	1 602, 1 590	1 418	1 260	1 088	540, 532	415
[Zn(tma) ₂]	1 715	1 615	1 608, 1 592	1 430	1 255	1 095	552, 543	435
[Zn(tan) ₂]	1 670	1 618	1 610, 1 600	1 435	1 265	1 105	550, 546	420

In the case of copper complexes two additional bands given under C=O are due to coordinated acetate group

signals (121.433, 122.683, 124.622 and 126.631 ppm) agree well with structure 1.

All the compounds show an intense molecular ion peak, P⁺/(P+1)⁺, and peaks due to (P-R₁ CO)⁺ and (P-R₂ CO)⁺. The most significant feature in the spec-

tra of all the compounds, is the presence of high intensity peaks at *m/z* 99, 100 and 126 and a peak of appreciable intensity due to (P-N₂)⁺. Nitrogen elimination from molecular ion is a characteristic of true azo compounds¹¹. The origin of the peak at *m/z* 126 can be explained by the formation of the ion radical T-N₂CH⁺

TABLE 3—¹H NMR SPECTRAL DATA (δ) OF DICARBONYLS AND THEIR Zn^{II} COMPLEXES

Compd.	R ₁	R ₂	Thiazolyl	Acidic proton
Htaa	2.45 (3H, s)	2.32 (3H, s)	6.60–7.25 (2H, m)	14.20
Httfa	2.48 (3H, s)	–	7.05–7.45 (2H, m)	14.48
Htba	2.52 (3H, s)	7.62–8.10 (5H, m)	7.10–7.40 (2H, m)	14.12
Htta	–	–	7.10–7.50 (5H, m)	13.85
Htma	2.38 (3H, s)	3.78 (3H, s)	6.60–7.30 (2H, m)	14.55
Htan	2.55 (3H, s)	7.35–7.60 (3H, s)	6.60–7.30 (2H, m)	14.50 (11.15) ^a
[Zn(taa) ₂]	2.52 (6H, s)	2.30 (6H, s)	6.70–7.50 (4H, m)	–
[Zn(ttfa) ₂]	2.55 (6H, s)	–	7.10–7.60 (4H, m)	–
[Zn(tba) ₂]	2.60 (6H, s)	7.70–8.25 (10H, m)	7.10–7.50 (4H, m)	–
[Zn(tta) ₂]	Complex multiplet at 6.90–7.95			–
[Zn(tma) ₂]	2.45 (6H, s)	3.75 (6H, m)	6.75–7.40 (4H, m)	–
[Zn(tan) ₂]	2.72 (6H, m)	7.60–7.90 (10H, m)	6.90–7.50 (4H, m)	11.20 ^a

^aThe signal due to anilic NH.

(T = thiazole ring) through the elimination of R₁CO and R₂CO from P⁺. If the present compound exists in the hydrazone form, the most facile reaction involves the cleavage of the N–N bond (as in the case of phenylazo derivatives of the 1,3-dicarbonyls)¹² and an ion of *m/z* 126 would not have originated. The ions of *m/z* 99 and 100 are undoubtedly due to the amine component, a characteristic of mass spectra of substituted azo compounds¹³. Thus the evidences support the azo-enol structure of the compounds.

Metal complexes: Elemental analytical data of the Cu^{II} complexes correspond to the composition [Cu(OAc)] and that of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes [ML₂]. Molar conductance data indicate their neutral character. Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Co^{II} complexes show normal magnetic moment in the range 1.78–1.82, 3.39–3.52 and 4.80–5.20 B.M. respectively.

In the infrared spectra of the complexes, the broad free ligand band at 2500–3500 cm⁻¹ cleared up, indicating the replacement of the chelated proton by metal ion and well-defined bands appeared at ~3050 cm⁻¹ due to ν_{C-H} . Spectra of the complexes containing methyl groups showed bands at ~2950 and ~2850 cm⁻¹ and complexes of Htan revealed additional band at ~3400 cm⁻¹ due to N–H of anilide. Spectra of all the copper complexes in this region are characterised by the presence of two bands at ~2980 and ~2870 cm⁻¹ assignable to the ν_{C-H} of acetate group.

Important bands below 2000 cm⁻¹ are presented in Table 2. From a comparison of the spectra of the complexes with the respective ligand spectrum, the following conclusions can be deduced. The free carbonyl band of the ligand is only marginally affected during complexation. The band due to $\nu_{C=N}$ (~1620 cm⁻¹) and $\nu_{N=N}$ shifted appreciable to lower values in the complexes which indicate that the thiazole nitrogen and one of the azo nitrogens are involved in bonding with metal ion. In spectra of all the copper complexes two additional bands at ~1615 and ~1300 cm⁻¹ can be assigned¹⁴ to the asymmetric and symmetric stretching of COO⁻ of acetate group. Since the difference of the two bands is >300 cm⁻¹, unidentate coordination of the acetate group is indicated. The ν_{C-O} band of the free ligand disappeared, instead a new band appeared at ~1100 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of all the complexes. Such a large shift indicates replacement of the enolic proton by the metal ion. The region 200–600 cm⁻¹ contains several absorptions not found in the ligand spectra assignable to ν_{M-N} and ν_{M-O} vibrations.

That the enol proton is replaced by the metal ion is evident from the absence of the low field signal of the ligand at ~14 ppm in the ¹H nmr spectra of the Zn^{II} complexes. The integrated intensities of all other signals (Table 3) agree well with the formulation of the complexes. The ¹³C nmr spectrum of Zn(taa)₂ showed eight signals (25.212, 33.244, 115.157, 136.376, 150.018, 169.562, 195.586 and 199.780 ppm) as expected of structure 2 of the compound. A comparison of chemical shift of these signals with of Htaa suggests that the acetyl carbonyl remains free in the complexes also.

The FAB mass spectra of all the copper complexes show a parent ion peak, $P^+/(P+1)^+$ based on ^{63}Cu and also a peak of almost half the intensity for ^{65}Cu , corresponding to the stoichiometry $[\text{CuLOAc}]$. However, peaks due to $(\text{CuL})^+$, $(\text{Cu}_2\text{L})^+$, $(\text{HL})^+$ are more intense than the parent ion peak. Peaks due to $(\text{CuT})^+$ is a characteristic feature of all the spectra. Similarly, spectra of the complexes containing CF_3 group show m/z values corresponding to CuCF_3 and $\text{Cu}(\text{CF}_3)_2$. Other prominent peaks are $(\text{P-R}_1\text{CO})^+$, $(\text{P-R}_2\text{CO})^+$, R_1CO , R_2CO and fragments of aryl rings(s). The mass spectra of the Ni^{II} , Co^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of Htaa show intense P^+ ion peak and also peaks due to $(\text{P-CH}_3\text{CO})^+$, $(\text{P-2CH}_3\text{CO})^+$, $[\text{M}(\text{taa})]^+$, $(\text{taa})^+$ and fragment species of $(\text{taa})^+$. The intensity of all the metal containing species including P^+ also shows peaks of intensity corresponding to the natural abundance of various isotopes of the metal ion.

Experimental

2-(2-Thiazolylazo)-1,3-dicarbonyls were synthesised as follows. 2-Aminothiazole (0.01 mol) was diazotised using H_2SO_4 and NaNO_2 as reported¹⁵. To the diazonium sulphate solution so obtained, urea was added to destroy excess nitrous acid. The solution was added dropwise to well-cooled (below 5°) and stirred solution of the 1,3-dicarbonyl (0.01 mol) in ethanol. Sodium acetate was added to adjust the pH of the mixture around 6. The precipitate formed was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from hot methanol/benzene.

Metal complexes were prepared by adding an aqueous solution of the metal(II) acetate (0.01 mol) to a methanolic solution of the ligand (0.02 mol). After stirring for about 3 h, the precipitated product was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from hot benzene.

Magnetic susceptibility was measured on Gouy balance at room temperature. Molar conductance of the complexes were determined in methanol (10^{-3} M). IR spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu IR 435 spectrophotometer, nmr spectra (CDCl_3) on a VX R Supercon Ft-NMR 300 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as reference and spectra using argon as the FAB gas (6 kV, 10

mA) and *m*-nitrobenzyl alcohol as the matrix on a JEOL SX 102/DA-6000 spectrometer from C.D.R.I., Lucknow.

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